

From single ethical rules to comprehensive ethical codes: the layer of ethical regulation on the map of international judicial institutions

Zuzana Trávníčková

In 2021, we registered four significant initiatives regarding ethical guidelines for judges of international courts: first, the Code of Judicial Ethics of the International Criminal Court was amended in January 2021. Second, the International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals revised its Code of Professional Conduct for Defence Counsel appearing before the Mechanism in May 2021. Third, the European Court of Human Rights adopted a Resolution on judicial ethics in June 2021. Finally, a new Code of Conduct for Members and Former Members of the Court of Justice of the European Union¹ was adopted at the end of September and entered into force in October 2021. What do these events say? Is this an isolated and coincidental activity of the three institutions mentioned above, or are they just three pieces in a large global puzzle of codes of ethics involving all international courts? The aim of this article is to sketch the layer of codes of ethics on the map of international courts.²

At first, we should shine the lights on the content of the term "judicial ethics". Judicial ethics is an example of professional ethics. In the judicial environment, the term "judicial ethics" is used for „*standards of conduct inherent in judicial office*“.³ These standards cover „*the personal independence, impartiality, and diligence of international adjudicators with respect to judicial and extra-judicial conduct*“.⁴ Judicial independence, impartiality, integrity, confidentiality and diligence are values defined and protected by the Code of Judicial Ethics adopted by the Judges of International Criminal Court (ICC) in 2005.⁵ Recent version of ICC Code of Judicial Ethics mentions also loyalty.⁶ Similarly, Resolution on Judicial Ethics, adopted by the European Court of Human Rights on June 2021 (and replacing Court's principles from June 2008)⁷ articulates the following principles underlying the criteria for judicial office: integrity, impartiality, independence, diligence and competence, discretion and confidentiality.⁸

¹ Code of Conduct for Members and former Members of the Court of Justice of the European Union. OJ C 483, 23.12.2016, p. 1–5.

² This article, on the other hand, does not deal with the substance of the codes of ethics and the comparison of their contents. It focuses only on the courts' own (self-regulatory) activity, and does not mention or analyse important initiatives emerging outside the 'courthouse' - e.g. Bangalore Principles of Judicial Conduct (2001), Burgh House Principles on the Independence of the International Judiciary (2004) or Bologna and Milan Global Code of Judicial Ethics (2015). It also leaves aside ethical rules and codes of conduct in international arbitration. To the content evaluation and comparison of existing codes of ethics see A Seibert-Fohr, 'International Judicial Ethics' in CPR Romano, KJ Alter, and Y Shany (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Adjudication* (OUP Oxford 2013) 757–78; T Dannenbaum, 'Regulation of the international bench' in WA Schabas and S Murphy (eds), *Research Handbook on International Courts and Tribunals* (Edward Elgar Cheltenham 2017) 377–406.

³ A Seibert-Fohr, 'Codes of Conduct for International Judges' (last updated December 2018) in H Ruiz Fabri (ed), *The Max Planck Encyclopedia of International Procedural Law* (Oxford University Press 2019–) <www.mpeipro.com> (accessed 15 August 2022), par. 1.

⁴ Ibid, par. 2.

⁵ International Criminal Court Code of Judicial Ethics (9 March 2005) ICC-BD/02-01-05.

⁶ International Criminal Court Code of Judicial Ethics (19 January 2021) ICC-BD/02-02-21.

⁷ European Court of Human Rights Resolution on Judicial Ethics (23 June 2008).

⁸ European Court of Human Rights Resolution on Judicial Ethics (21 June 2021).

The clearer the picture of the particular values and principles becomes, that are embodied in judicial ethics and that appear across the ethical rules - impartiality, independence and integrity⁹ - the more familiar this picture becomes. Independence and impartiality are requirements already imposed on judges by Art. 2 and Art. 20 of the Statute of the Permanent Court of International Justice.¹⁰ As in other respects, the wording of the ICJ Statute on the impartiality and independence of judges is identical in content and numbering to the wording of the PCIJ Statute (Art. 2 and Art. 20 of the ICJ Statute)¹¹. In addition to the prior regime, the ICJ Statute contains a provision on the independent exercise of the duties of the agents, counsel, and advocates of parties before the Court (art. 42). Also, the concept and formulation of impartiality and independence of judges is almost in the same way embraced by the Statute of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea (Articles 2 and 11 of the ITLOS Statute).¹² A subtle difference in wording can be found in the definition of the requirements for the person of a judge. In the case of the ICJ it must be "persons of high moral character" (Art. 2 ICJ Statute, identically also Art. 2 of PCIJ Statute), in the case of ITLOS the requirement is formulated in a more modern way and reads: "persons enjoying the highest reputation for fairness and integrity" (Art. 2 par. 1 ITLOS Statute). The provisions of the Statute on impartiality and independence are reflected in the Rules of Procedure of the ICJ and ITLOS and, in the case of the Hague Court, also in the Practice Directions VII and VIII.¹³

Compared to the codes of ethics – as independent self-regulating documents - of other judicial institutions (ICC, ECtHR, ECJ), the formal approach of the previously mentioned global courts to ethical issues appears relatively modest. The rules contained in the modern codes of ethics of international courts have been inherent and natural to the courts since their inception (whether in the 1920s, 1940s, 1950s, 1990s or elsewhere) and their basic formulation – at least in relation to judges - is always to be found in the relevant Statute. At the same time, however, a sort of "fashion for ethical codification" in the post-2000 period is apparent.

The table 1 outlines the development of the adoption of codes of ethics for judges and other legal professionals involved in international judicial proceedings. The table intentionally does not mention ICJ, ITLOS, Inter-American Court for Human Rights, African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights and ILO Administrative Tribunal, because these courts have not (yet) adopted the Code of Ethics (Code of Conduct) as a selfstanding document.

Table 1. Adoption of complex ethical regulations within international judicial bodies

Year	Court/Organisation	Document
1996	World Trade Organisation (WTO)	Rules of conduct for the understanding on rules and procedures governing the settlement of disputes

⁹ Mindaugas Šimonis names these three values „the three big ‘I’“. ŠIMONIS, Mindaugas. The role of judicial ethics in court administration: from setting the objectives to practical implementation. *Baltic journal of law & politics*, 2017, Vol. 10, No. 1, p. 94.

¹⁰ League of Nations Statute of the Permanent Court of International Justice (16 December 1920) Series D No 1. Art. 2 states, that: „*The Permanent Court of International Justice shall be composed of a body of independent judges...*“ and Art. 20 states, that: „*Every member of the Court shall, before taking up his duties, make a solemn declaration in open Court that he will exercise his powers impartially and conscientiously.*“

¹¹ Statute of the International Court of Justice (adopted 26 June 1945, entered into force 24 October 1945) Cmd 7015 TS No 67 (1946).

¹² Statute of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea, Annex VI to the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (concluded 10 December 1982, entered into force 16 November 1994) 1833 UNTS 561.

¹³ Practice Directions of the International Court of Justice (Adopted on 7 February 2002) <<https://www.icj-cij.org/en/practice-directions>> (accessed 15 August 2022).

1997	International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY)	Code of Professional Conduct for Counsel Appearing before the International Tribunal
1998	International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR)	Code of Professional Conduct for Defence Counsel
1999	ICTR	Standards Of Professional Conduct for Prosecution Counsel
	ICTY	Standards of Professional Conduct for Prosecution Counsel
2005	International Criminal Court (ICC)	Code of Professional Conduct for Counsel
	ICC	Code of Judicial Ethics (amended in 2021)
2007	Court of Justice of the European Communities (CJEU)	Code of Conduct
2008	European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR)	Resolution on Judicial Ethics
2009	ICTY	Code of Professional Conduct <i>for</i> Counsel Appearing before the International Criminal Tribunal (Amended in 2002, 2006 and 2009)
2011	UN Dispute Tribunal, UN Appeal Tribunal (UNDT, UNAT)	Code of conduct for the judges of the UNDT and UNAT
	Special Tribunal for Lebanon (STL)	Code of Professional Conduct for Counsel Appearing Before the Tribunal
2012	STL	Code of Professional Conduct for Defence Counsel and Legal Representatives of Victims appearing before the STL (amended in 2019)
	International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals (IRMCT)	Code of professional conduct for Defence Counsel appearing before the Mechanism
2013	Caribbean Court of Justice (CCJ)	Code of Judicial Conduct
2015	UNDT, UNAT	Mechanism for addressing complaints regarding alleged misconduct or incapacity of the judges of UNDT and UNAT
2016	CJEU	Code of Conduct for Members and former Members of the CJEU
	UNDT, UNAT	Code of conduct for legal representatives and litigants in person
	ICC	Code of professional conduct for the judges of the Tribunal
	ICTY	Code of professional conduct for the judges of the Tribunal
	STL	Code od professional conduct for the judges of the STL
2017	IRMCT	Code of Ethics for Interpreters and Translators Employed by the Mechanism for International Criminal Tribunals
2018	IRMCT	Code of Professional Conduct for the Judges of the Mechanism
2019	IRMCT	Code of Ethics for Interpreters and Translators Employed by the International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals
2020	CCJ	Code of Judicial Conduct
2021	ECtHR	Resolution on Judicial Ethics
	IRMCT	Code of professional conduct for Defence Counsel appearing before the Mechanism
	CJEU	Code of Conduct for Members and former Members of the CJEU

Source: Author.

The overview outlines the dynamics of "ethical codification", its rapid take-off since the late 1990s and its enduring pace in the third millennium. A significant role is played by international criminal tribunals,

which formulate and fine-tune codes of conduct on an ongoing and distinct basis for the different groups of professionals involved in international criminal proceedings (besides judges, these include prosecution counsels, defence counsels, victim representatives, translators and interpreters). Modern international criminal justice has been accompanied by codes of ethics since its emergence, and as Table 1 shows, none of the international criminal tribunals established since the 1990s can do without a code of ethics.

The homogeneity that we observe in the approach to codes of ethics in criminal tribunals is not seen in the human rights courts environment; the European court has a code of ethics for judges, ad hoc judges and former judges, but the Inter-American and African courts do not. The two administrative tribunals also take a different approach; the ILO Administrative tribunal does not have a code of conduct, the UNDT adopted one in 2011,¹⁴ shortly after its creation in 2009.

With the exception of ITLOS (which was created under UNCLOS 1982 and established in 1994), all judicial institutions created after 1990 have adopted codes of ethics. The examples of the WTO,¹⁵ ICC, CCJ, UNDT/UNAT suggest that a code of conduct (at least for judges) is so called "must-be", is one of the fundamental matters that every new court addressed soon after its formation.

Returning to the analogy of ethical rules as layers on the map of international justice, we can distinguish three situations.

1. The ethical rules are formulated only in a rudimentary and brief form in a few provisions in the founding document (ICJ, ITLOS, ILO AT). A common feature of the courts in the first group is a certain "age-oldness" and traditionality. The roots of the ILO AT go back to 1927. The ICJ is usually seen as the successor to the Permanent Court of International Justice (1922-1946). Although the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea was not treaty-anchored and created until later, the International Court of Justice was the inspiration for its composition and procedures. At the time of their creation, ethical issues were limited to impartiality and independence and briefly regulated in their Statutes. They have not yet joined the later practice of ethical codification and it is not clear that they are in any way preparing to do so. This traditional relationship to ethical issues is also inherent in the Inter-American and African human rights courts.
2. The rules of conduct of judges are elaborated beyond the Statute in a stand-alone document (code of ethics, code of conduct), usually adopted by the Court itself (not by the State parties of the Statute as an international treaty), the regulation is more detailed. This practice is typical for regional courts - CJEU, ECtHR, CCJ; although, of course, it is not the case that all regional courts have a code of ethics. The Inter-American Court for Human Rights and the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights have not yet adopted a code of conduct or code of ethics as a stand-alone document. In the case of the European courts, the codes of ethics were adopted after a longer time lag (several decades) after the courts were established; in the case of the Caribbean court of justice (international treaty of 2001, the court has been operating since 2005), the time lag was considerably shorter.

¹⁴ Code of Conduct for the Judges of the United Nations Dispute Tribunal and the United Nations Appeals Tribunal (adopted 9 December 2011) A/RES/66/106.

¹⁵ World Trade Organization Rules of conduct for the understanding on rules and procedures governing the settlement of disputes (11 December 1996) WT/DSB/RC/1 (WTO Rules of Conduct).

3. A group of international tribunals (ICTY,¹⁶ ICTR, IRMCT,¹⁷ STL,¹⁸ ICC¹⁹) that have taken the path of developing ethical regulation in the form of multiple parallel rules, targeting not only judges but also other professionals in the proceedings (defence counsel, prosecution counsel, witnesses and interpreters). Across the second and third group, we can further identify a subset of courts (UNDT and IRMCT) that are not satisfied with the preventive force of the codes and have introduced a complaints mechanism²⁰ for alleged misconduct or incapacity of the judges.

The adoption of codes of ethics is undoubtedly a recent issue. For international courts established after 1990, the adoption of a code of conduct/ ethics is the rule (with the exception of ITLOS, which was established by UNCLOS adopted in 1982, and the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, whose first judges were elected in 2006). As for the courts established earlier, their relationship to codes of ethics varies. The traditional courts associated with the United Nations (ICJ, ILO AT) do not deal with separate codes of ethics and rely on the specific provisions on impartiality and independence included in their Statutes. On the other hand, regional European courts (connected to the Council of Europe or the European Union) have joined in the practice of declaring codes of ethics.

International criminal tribunals play a leading role in the adoption of codes of ethics. Their receptivity to and confidence in ethical codification is manifested, among other things, by the formulation of ethical rules not only for judges but also for other legal professionals who act for the prosecution, the defence or witnesses in international criminal proceedings.

Most courts that have previously decided to adopt a code of ethics have subsequently developed it. All codes of ethics adopted after 2013 are additions or "amendments" to earlier codes, and the vast majority of current codes are currently in their second version.

The practice of adopting codes of ethics across international courts can now be described as longstanding, common to different types of international courts, and widespread and representative. While it is not a practice in which all international courts have engaged, its duration and prevalence show that it is not a 'fad' but an integral aspect of the self-definition of actors in international justice.

¹⁶ International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia Code of professional conduct for the judges of the Tribunal (6 July 2016) S/2016/976 Enclosure VII; Prosecutor's Regulation No 2, 'Standards of Professional Conduct for Prosecution Counsel' (14 September 1999); International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia, 'Code of Professional Conduct for Counsel Appearing before the International Tribunal' (12 June 1997).

¹⁷ Code of Professional Conduct for the Judges of the Mechanism for International Criminal Tribunals (9 April 2018) IRMCT/14/Rev.1.

¹⁸ Code of Professional Conduct for the Judges of the Special Tribunal for Lebanon (27 September 2016) STL-CC-2016-04; Special Tribunal for Lebanon, 'Code of Professional Conduct for Counsel Appearing Before the Special Tribunal for Lebanon' (28 February 2011); Special Tribunal for Lebanon 'Code of Professional Conduct for Defence Counsel and Legal Representatives of Victims appearing before the Special Tribunal for Lebanon' (14 December 2012).

¹⁹ International Criminal Court, Office of the Prosecutor, 'Code of Conduct for the Office of the Prosecutor' (5 September 2013) OTP2013/024322.

²⁰ A Seibert-Fohr, 'Codes of Conduct for International Judges', par. 23.